

The Effect of Product Purchase Boycott Activities by Consumers on Stock Prices

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ABSTRACT

The Israeli-Hamas conflict in the Gaza Strip, which began on October 7, 2023, has had a significant impact on companies currently affiliated with Israel and its subsidiaries. Shares of companies allegedly affiliated with Israel experienced a decline in stock capitalization. This happened due to a decline in consumer demand, worker strikes, and alleged boycotts of these companies. The purpose of this study is to determine the effect of product boycotts on stock prices. The research sample is as many as 35 companies affiliated with Israel listed on the Jakarta Stock Exchange. The research method used is differential test analysis using the Paired Sample test. The results of the study show that there is an effect of the boycott on the stock price at a significance of 10%. However, at a significance level of 5%, it shows no influence. The results of this study can provide input to companies to be careful in providing support to parties who do not have empathy for humanity.

KEYWORDS: boycott, Palestinian-Israeli conflict. Israeli products, stock prices

I. INTRODUCTION

Palestinian-Israeli conflict since October 7, 2023, it is a major concern around the world today. Based on data from the UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs, there are 11,261 Palestinian casualties in the Gaza Strip and the West Bank, and some of the victims are children. This conflict has turned into a humanitarian tragedy. Support from various countries has also emerged in various forms, both morally and materially, strengthening its position as a global issue (Boys, 2023). In Indonesia, the above also happens, especially with the support of the Indonesian Ulema Council Commission. The MUI Fatwa Commission released the Latest Fatwa on November 10, 2023. The fatwa Number 83 of 2023 contains the Law on Support for the Palestinian Struggle. Through the fatwa, the MUI indirectly states that Muslims as much as possible to avoid using products and transactions with parties allegedly affiliated with Israel and its allies (Nadya Zahira, 2023)

As a result, several companies whose products were targeted by the Israeli boycott recorded a decrease in profits in the third quarter of 2023. Observers also predict that this decline will occur as long as the boycott is carried out seriously. For example, retail chain issuer PT Mitra Adiperkasa Tbk (MAPI) recorded a net profit for the current period attributable to owners of the parent entity of IDR 1.49

trillion in the third quarter of 2023, down 5.18% year-on-year (yoy) from IDR 1.57 trillion. MAPI is the parent issuer of the management of the Starbucks beverage brand in Indonesia through its subsidiary PT MAP Boga Adiperkasa Tbk. (Nadya Zahira, 2023). Likewise, the Pizza Hut restaurant, under PT Sarimelati Kencana Tbk (PZZA) recorded a net loss for the current year until the third quarter of 2023 of IDR 38.95 billion. On the other hand, the issuer that manages KFC Indonesia's fast food restaurant, PT Fast Food Indonesia Tbk (FAST) recorded a net loss of IDR 152.41 billion until the third quarter of this year. This loss swelled by 815.69% compared to the previous year's loss of IDR 17.16 billion (Nadya Zahira, 2023)

The boycott can have a significant impact on the company's profit decline, which means it also has an impact on the company's performance and reputation. The performance of a company is a reflection of the intrinsic value of its stock price. If the company has a good performance. Then the stock price will increase. Consequences of poor company performance PT MAP Boga Adiperkasa Tbk (MAPB) Its shares have declined since the call for a boycott of Israeli-affiliated products. At the end of December 2023, MAPB shares were at the level of IDR 1,990 per share and stagnant for one minggu. It is estimated that the movement of MAPB shares will also continue to be stagnant, even though in the month before the boycott

activity, its shares experienced an increase of 1.79%. (Nadya Zahira, 2023). Boycott activities also result in a decrease in revenue. Net profit and share price of PT PT Unilever Indonesia Tbk (UNVR), Based on RTI Business data, revenue decreased by 6.3%, net profit by 10.51% and share price by 34.70% in the last six months after the boycott activity (NABILA, 2024). Based on the description above, this study is intended to examine the influence of boycott activities on stock prices. The purpose of this research is to provide input to companies on matters related to boycott activities that can cause losses to the company.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Definition of Boycott

A boycott is when a consumer refuses to buy goods from a company, and tries to persuade other consumers to achieve the same goal. With the boycott, consumers aim to reduce sales of target companies' products, reduce their profits, and damage their image in the market (KESER & SÖĞÜTLÜ, 2023). Boycott activities by consumers are considered a form of political consumerism in which consumers use their purchasing power to achieve political, social, environmental, or ethical goals (Natacha Jesus-Silva et al., 2023).

Serhan (2015) stated that a boycott is a strategy to reject something that is not in accordance with the values of a certain group. Therefore, a boycott can mean an attempt to urge consumers to refrain from making purchases of certain products in the market. A number of factors that have the potential to trigger a consumer boycott are religious, war, political, economic, cultural, environmental, and ethical reasons. Nevertheless, there is no factor ranking that indicates which factors are the most influential. However, there are differences in boycott activities in developed and developing countries. Boycott campaigns in developed countries are largely influenced by economic factors. However, in developing countries, boycott calls and campaigns are influenced by religious or ethical reasons (Al Serhan & Boukrami).

Motivation for Boycott Activities

Boycotts can serve as a way to raise awareness about social issues, mobilize consumers, and allow companies to focus on the social aspect. Boycotts can draw attention to various social problems, such as labor rights violations, human rights violations, and discriminatory practices. By boycotting companies related to these issues, consumers are showing their support for social justice. Individual consumers are encouraged to boycott because of instrumental motivations. The purpose of the boycott can be explicitly stated, i.e. to influence policy changes of the target company, such as asking the company to lower prices, signing union contracts. The message conveyed exponentially also aims to signal to other consumers about the need for the boycott activity.

Individual consumers can also be encouraged to boycott non-instrumental ones that are marked by unclear goals. Consumers protest target companies and vent their frustrations as a means of expression and self-realization. If individual consumers are driven based on non-instrumental motivations, the decision to boycott is not intended to attract other consumers to boycott. Non-instrumental motivation can also be seen as a motivation for self-improvement. Based on this theory, participation in boycott activities can increase self-esteem, because it has carried out a moral obligation. This motivation is also based on avoiding feelings of discomfort due to buying company products that are considered unethical. This is a response to social pressure based on intrinsic rewards. By participating in boycott activities, individual consumers expect others to view them positively. Non-instrumental motivation also aims at the target company to be dissolved (Makarem & Jae, 2020).

Boycott Activities, Consumer Behavior and Company Performance

The impulse to boycott is triggered because of consumers' assessment of certain events that can affect consumers emotionally, which in turn affects their behavior. If a company is perceived as unethical or unfair, consumers will experience negative emotions such as anger. This emotion can cause a negative behavioral response so that consumers behave anti-consumption. In Indonesia, the boycott of Israeli-affiliated products has created a new habit for consumers to prefer the consumption of local products. National products experienced an increase in sales and therefore could create new jobs (AULIA) The Indonesian Shopping Center Retailers and Tenants Association (Hippindo) revealed that the boycott of pro Israel carried out by the Indonesian people has had an impact on the retail and restaurant sectors. As a result, it occurred Decline in sales up to 40 percent in the sector (Septyaningsih, 2023). Especially for retail products, the decline occurred in some areas around 3-4% during the boycott call that lasted less than a week (Rachmawati, 2023).

Boycott activities cause a change in consumer attitudes and intention to buy the target company's products. Boycott activities can harm the company's image and adversely affect its financial performance, especially on sales value. The sales value reflects the success of the investment in the previous period, which can be used to predict future growth. It can also indicate the company's demand and competitiveness. Sales growth is one of the indicators of a company's growth. Good company conditions increase demand for stocks and can trigger an increase in stock prices (Susilowati et al., 2020)

Effect of Boycott Activities on Stock Prices

Boycott activities by consumers are anti-consumption behavior, which means that the boycotters are consumers who do not consume certain products and services due to

environmental, political, ethical, or social problems. Formally, a boycott can be defined as the attempt of one or more parties to achieve a specific goal by urging individual consumers to refrain from making purchases of the target company's products. Consumer boycotts are also described as refusal to conduct market transactions with companies that are the target of the boycott (Natacha Jesus-Silva et al., 2023). From an economic perspective, boycott of product purchases by consumers can have a significant impact on the company's reputation and financial performance and can jeopardize the competitive advantage between companies and countries. Companies that are the target of boycotts are often publicized negatively as a result of damage to their brand image, and a decline in sales. If this boycott activity lasts for a long time on a sustainable basis, this will cause large financial losses for the company.

A rational investor, in making investment decisions, financial information is a very important factor. An investor will buy shares of a company if the shares in the company are of high value based on its financial performance. High financial performance can provide assurance that the company will grow sustainably in the next few years. As a result, the demand for the purchase of shares of well-performing companies will increase, which will ultimately increase the market price of the company's shares. So, a company's financial performance is a reflection of the intrinsic value of its stock price. The stock price of companies that perform well will be higher. Understanding the consequences of boycotts by consumers from an economic perspective can provide insight into the potential impact of boycotts as a driver of sustainable business practices. International companies often respond by implementing reforms, improving working conditions, and implementing sustainable business practices. This in the long run could lead to stronger engagement among stakeholders and relevant institutions as well as international agreements. (Natacha Jesus-Silva et al., 2023)

Previous Research

A number of studies on the relationship of an event affecting stock prices have been carried out by Iis Nurashia (2023) exploring the impact of the correction in the stock price of products related to Israel due to the Boycott, Divestment, and Sanctions (BDS) movement based on data from the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) in 2023. The global boycott that began on October 10, 2023, or 3 days after Israel's genocidal act against Palestine, has an impact on the stock value of companies from countries that allegedly support the action. The author shows this through 3 issuers that manage 3 brands from that country, namely Starbucks, KFC, and Unilever. The test results showed that there was no difference in stock prices before and after the announcement of the boycott. However, after the MUI issued fatwa No. 83 in 2023 showing support for Palestine, the stock price has decreased, so there is a striking

difference between the stock price before the BDS action after the MUI decision. The results of subsequent tests showed that there was a significant difference between the stock price after BDS (Boycott, Divestment, and Sanctions) and the share price after the MUI fatwa was issued. Thus, it can be concluded that the BDS movement in Indonesia does not have a significant influence because the stock price does not show a difference before and after the announcement of the movement. The significant impact was proven after this action was strengthened by the issuance of the MUI fatwa regarding the law in support of Palestine. This is due to the MUI's fatwa which is very influential among Indonesian Muslims. Most of the Indonesian population who are Muslims tend to follow the MUI fatwa, which is a representation of the views of Muslim scholars in Indonesia.

The events of military aggression in the Israeli-Hamas conflict have had a significant influence from various countries, as well as opposition to the genocide committed by Israel against Palestinians. Solidarity actions are also taking place in various countries in an effort to provide support for Palestinian independence and abolish colonialism in the world. The condemnation carried out by the public is a form of product boycott as a protest against genocide. The impact of the boycott action can be seen in the decline in the stock prices of 30 companies from Israel's supporting countries, namely: America, Germany, France, the United Kingdom, and Switzerland, this is due to investors' anxiety about the threat of a boycott by the international community. The stability of the company's income can also be threatened due to the existence of a war conflict that the public criticizes for Israel's cruel actions. Allegedly, many companies from countries that support Israel provide discounts on products at every outlet in various countries to reduce the chances of competitors entering and beating similar products.

The decline in the stock price reached 2,774 USD, with a significant level of 0.005, indicating a significant decline in the stock price. Therefore, the hypothesis that the Israel-Hamas war affects stock prices is acceptable (Annisa Nadiyah Rahmani; AoEJ; Academy of Education Journal). The study (Arum, 2023) aims to analyze the difference in the market value of companies as a result of the ban on support for MUI fatwa No. 83 of 2023 which resulted in a boycott of the products of companies affiliated with Israel. His research findings indicated that the existence of a boycott triggered a decline in the market value of the company, especially within a 3-day time window, but when the time window was extended to 5 and 10 days, the results showed no significant difference in the market value of the company due to the boycott. The results of the study provide information for investors and parties related to the company in determining company/financial strategies when facing events that cause uncertainty such as product boycotts

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This study is a comparative study, that is, a study that compares two or more phenomena to identify whether there is a difference or not. This study intends to compare the stock prices of companies before and after the boycott activity. The research sample is the share prices of 35 companies affiliated with Israel listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in the period from March 7, 2023 to May 7, 2024. Data analysis using a different test, Paired Sample T test.

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS

A. Descriptive Stock Price after Boycott

The share prices of Israeli-affiliated companies in Indonesia in the period after the boycott show different conditions. For example, the shares of PT MAP Boga Adiperkasa Tbk as the company that manages the Starbucks beverage brand, the stock price fluctuates and tends to be stagnant (Grafik 1). It is another case with the company that manages the Pizza Hut restaurant, PT Sarimelati Kencana Tbk (PZZA). The company's share price has experienced a significant decline (Chart 2). Meanwhile, the share price of PT Unilever Tbk, a pro-Israel food and cosmetic product manufacturing company, initially declined until May 2024, the trend indicates that the share price will increase again (Graphic 3)

Graph 1. PT MAP Boga Adiperkasa Tbk's share price after the boycott (Source: investing.com)

Graph 2. PT Sarimelati Kencana Tbk Share Price (Source: investing.com)

Graph 3. PT Unilever Tbk share price (Source: investing.com)

B. Analysis of Difference Tests

To find out if there is an effect of boycott activities on stock prices, a different test is carried out using the Paired Sample test. The sample of the study was 35 average share prices of Israeli-affiliated companies in the 7 months before the boycott (March 7 – October 7, 2023) and 7 months after the boycott (October 8, 2023 – May 2024). The results of the analysis are presented in table 1. The results of the analysis show that there is no difference in the average stock price before and after the boycott activity at the significance level (α)= 5% (p value > 0.05), which indicates that there is no effect of the boycott on the stock price. Will remain if the significance rate = 10%, the results of the analysis show that there is a difference in the stock price before and after the boycott activity (p value < 0.1), which means that there is an effect of the boycott activity on the stock price.

Table 1. Results of Analysis of Different Tests

Paired Differences	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
				Lower	Upper			
Pre 1 - Post 1	1824.143	5711.478	805.418	-2885.104	57.818	-1.912	34	.057

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results showed different results when using a significance level (α) of 5% and 10%. Boycott activities have no effect on stock prices at a significance level of 5%, while at a significance level of 10%, boycott activities have an effect on stock prices. This happens because there are several companies whose stock prices tend to fall, stagnate, or increase after the boycott. Overall, some of the company's stock prices tend to fall in the first 3 months after the boycott and increase again and will return to their original prices 7 months after the boycott. This study only compares conditions in the 7-month period before and after the boycott activity, so the results of the study tend to show that the boycott activity has no effect on the stock price. This is because in the long term the company has a new strategy to improve its company performance, by improving the company's image which can ultimately increase its revenue.

Various methods that can be applied by companies to improve the company's image. For example, PT Unilever Tbk affirms its commitment to always prioritizing human rights values, as well as respecting and understanding the culture, norms, and values in the area. The company seeks to convince the public that the products it produces reflect Islamic values, such as shampoo products for women wearing hijab. In addition, the company has made various product innovations and programs in a more organized manner through the Muslim Centre of Excellence (MCoE) (Nilasari, 2023)

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